

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: Yuichiro Nakazawa

Email: Yuichiro_Nakazawa@kagome.co.jp

Date submitted: November 11, 2025

Date requested by: Click or tap to enter a date.

Search Topic or Title:

Effect of lycopene intake on protection against UV-induced skin damage

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

- This is my first submission This is submitted after feedback
 This is an update (the search has been previously used in an evidence syntheses)

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

- This is my first submission This is submitted after feedback
 This is an update (the search has been previously used in an evidence syntheses)

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

The Cochrane Library/Wiley

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

In healthy adult subjects, does oral intake of lycopene improve vascular endothelial function compared to oral intake of a test product that does not contain lycopene or has extremely low lycopene concentration compared to the intervention, or no intervention?

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICO, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., **P**atient, **I**ntervention, **C**omparison, **O**utcome, and **S**tudy Design — as applicable)

P Healthy adult subjects (excluding minors, pregnant women, women planning pregnancy, and lactating women).

I Oral intake of lycopene

C Oral intake of a test product that does not contain lycopene or has extremely low lycopene concentration compared to the intervention, or no intervention

O Skin photoprotection assessed by erythema (a* value), minimal erythema dose (MED), skin lightness (L* value), erythema index, or D30

S Randomized controlled trials, quasi-randomized controlled trials, non-randomized controlled trials

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

Yes No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Click or tap here to enter text.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

Click or tap here to enter text.

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

#1 (lycopene* OR Polycopene OR Pro-Lycopene OR Pro Lycopene OR LYC-O-MATO OR LYCOMATO OR LYC O MATO OR All-trans-Lycopene):ti,ab,kw 776
#2 MeSH descriptor: [Lycopene] explode all trees 304
#3 MeSH descriptor: [Solanum lycopersicum] explode all trees 146
#4 (tomato OR tomatoes OR solanum lycopersicum OR lycopersicon esculentum OR watermelon OR water melon):ti,ab,kw 856
#5 #1 OR #2 OR #3 OR #4 1,383
#6 MeSH descriptor: [Skin Disease] explode all trees 58,695
#7 (ultraviolet OR UV OR photodamage OR photoexposure OR skin OR erythema OR redness OR sunburn OR minimal erythema dose OR MED OR erythema index OR skin color OR pigmentation):ti,ab,kw 157,824
#8 #6 OR #7 198,886
#9 #5 AND #8 in Trials 242

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: Non-Disclosure

Email: Non-Disclosure

Date completed: November 28, 2025

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were "revision required," this response must be "revisions required.").

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

※pubmed で使用されていた Mesh を追加したり、suntan を追加した検索も行いましたが、結果件数に影響がないようなのでこのままでよいかと思えます。

Acknowledgement

Do you wish to be acknowledged?

(If yes, the review team will be advised to add an acknowledgement to any publications related to this work).

Yes No

Please use the following acknowledgement template to provide your name, postnominals, and institutional affiliation as you would like them presented

We thank [NAME], [POSTNOMINALS (MLS, AHIP, etc.)] (Affiliated institution) for peer review of the submitted search strategy.

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please use the following citation for the PRESS checklist when citing the use of PRESS in a journal publication

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment. *PRESS – Peer Review of Electronic Search Strategies: 2015 Guideline Explanation and Elaboration (PRESS E&E)*. Ottawa: CADTH; 2016 Jan. <https://www.cadth.ca/press-peer-review-electronic-search-strategies-0>

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: Yuichiro Nakazawa

Email: Yuichiro_Nakazawa@kagome.co.jp

Date submitted: November 11, 2025

Date requested by: Click or tap to enter a date.

Search Topic or Title:

Effect of lycopene intake on protection against UV-induced skin damage

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

- This is my first submission This is submitted after feedback
 This is an update (the search has been previously used in an evidence syntheses)

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

- This is my first submission This is submitted after feedback
 This is an update (the search has been previously used in an evidence syntheses)

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

ClinicalTrials.gov

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

ClinicalTrials.gov

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

In healthy adult subjects, does oral intake of lycopene improve vascular endothelial function compared to oral intake of a test product that does not contain lycopene or has extremely low lycopene concentration compared to the intervention, or no intervention?

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICO, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., **P**atient, **I**ntervention, **C**omparison, **O**utcome, and **S**tudy Design — as applicable)

P Healthy adult subjects (excluding minors, pregnant women, women planning pregnancy, and lactating women).

I Oral intake of lycopene

C Oral intake of a test product that does not contain lycopene or has extremely low lycopene concentration compared to the intervention, or no intervention

O Skin photoprotection assessed by erythema (a* value), minimal erythema dose (MED), skin lightness (L* value), erythema index, or D30

S Randomized controlled trials, quasi-randomized controlled trials, non-randomized controlled trials

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

Yes No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Click or tap here to enter text.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

Click or tap here to enter text.

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

#1 (lycopene* OR "Lycopene, (13-cis)-isomer" OR "Lycopene, (7-cis,7'-cis,9-cis,9'-cis)-isomer -" OR "Prolycopene" OR "Pro-Lycopene" OR "Pro Lycopene" OR "Lycopene, (cis)-isomer" OR "LYC-O-MATO" OR "LYCOMATO" OR "LYC O MATO" OR "All-trans-Lycopene" OR "All trans Lycopene") in Other terms 125

#2 (lycopene* OR "Lycopene, (13-cis)-isomer" OR "Lycopene, (7-cis,7'-cis,9-cis,9'-cis)-isomer -" OR "Prolycopene" OR "Pro-Lycopene" OR "Pro Lycopene" OR "Lycopene, (cis)-isomer" OR "LYC-O-MATO" OR "LYCOMATO" OR "LYC O MATO" OR "All-trans-Lycopene" OR "All trans Lycopene") in Intervention/treatmen 89

#3 #1 OR #2 125

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: Non-Disclosure

Email: Non-Disclosure

Date completed: November 28, 2025

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were “revision required,” this response must be “revisions required.”).

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Acknowledgement

Do you wish to be acknowledged?

(If yes, the review team will be advised to add an acknowledgement to any publications related to this work).

Yes No

Please use the following acknowledgement template to provide your name, postnominals, and institutional affiliation as you would like them presented

We thank [NAME], [POSTNOMINALS (MLS, AHIP, etc.)] (Affiliated institution) for peer review of the submitted search strategy.

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please use the following citation for the PRESS checklist when citing the use of PRESS in a journal publication

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment. *PRESS – Peer Review of Electronic Search Strategies: 2015 Guideline Explanation and Elaboration (PRESS E&E)*. Ottawa: CADTH; 2016 Jan. <https://www.cadth.ca/press-peer-review-electronic-search-strategies-0>

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: Yuichiro Nakazawa

Email: Yuichiro_Nakazawa@kagome.co.jp

Date submitted: November 11, 2025

Date requested by: Click or tap to enter a date.

Search Topic or Title:

Effect of lycopene intake on protection against UV-induced skin damage

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

- This is my first submission
- This is submitted after feedback
- This is an update (the search has been previously used in an evidence syntheses)

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

- This is my first submission
- This is submitted after feedback
- This is an update (the search has been previously used in an evidence syntheses)

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

Global Index Medicus

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

Global Index Medicus

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

In healthy adult subjects, does oral intake of lycopene improve vascular endothelial function compared to oral intake of a test product that does not contain lycopene or has extremely low lycopene concentration compared to the intervention, or no intervention?

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICOs, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., **P**atient, **I**ntervention, **C**omparison, **O**utcome, and **S**tudy Design — as applicable)

P Healthy adult subjects (excluding minors, pregnant women, women planning pregnancy, and lactating women).

I Oral intake of lycopene

C Oral intake of a test product that does not contain lycopene or has extremely low lycopene concentration compared to the intervention, or no intervention

O Skin photoprotection assessed by erythema (a* value), minimal erythema dose (MED), skin lightness (L* value), erythema index, or D30

S Randomized controlled trials, quasi-randomized controlled trials, non-randomized controlled trials

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

Yes No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Click or tap here to enter text.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

Click or tap here to enter text.

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

#1 ((lycopene OR "Lycopene, (13-cis)-isomer" OR "Lycopene, (7-cis,7'-cis,9-cis,9'-cis)-isomer -" OR "Prolycopene" OR "Pro-Lycopene" OR "Pro Lycopene" OR "Lycopene, (cis)-isomer" OR "LYC-O-MATO" OR "LYCOMATO" OR "LYC O MATO" OR "All-trans-Lycopene" OR "All trans Lycopene") OR (mh:"lycopene")) AND ((random* OR trial* OR placebo) OR mh:("Clinical Study" OR "Clinical Trial" OR "Randomized Controlled Trial" OR "Controlled Clinical Trial" OR "Epidemiologic Studies")) in Title, abstract, subject 69

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: Non-Disclosure

Email: Non-Disclosure

Date completed: November 27, 2025

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were “revision required,” this response must be “revisions required.”).

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

※検証時点では、78件がヒットするようです。恐れ入りますが、ご確認いただけますでしょうか。

The screenshot shows the Global Index Medicus search interface. The search bar contains the query: ((lycopene OR "Lycopene, (13-cis)-isomer" OR "Lycopene, (7-cis,7'-cis,9-cis,9'-cis)-isomer-" OF. The first search result is highlighted with a red box and includes the following information:

- Title:** Lycopene supplementation reduces inflammatory, histopathological and DNA damage in an acute lung injury rabbit model
- Abstract:** Lycopene supplementation significantly reduces inflammation, histological injury, and DNA damage in a lung injury model. High-frequency oscillatory ventilation with or without lycopene also improves oxygenation compared to conventional mechanical ventilation alone. Lycopene supplementation offers protection against lung injuries under both ventilatory modes, improving outcomes in severe lung conditions.
- Authors:** Fioretto, José Roberto; Klefens, Susiane Oliveira; Carpi, Mário Ferreira; Moraes, Marcos Aurélio; Bonatto, Rossano César; Ferreira, Ana Lúcia Anjos; Corrêa, Camila Renata; Kurokawa, Cilmerv

Acknowledgement

Do you wish to be acknowledged?

(If yes, the review team will be advised to add an acknowledgement to any publications related to this work).

Yes No

Please use the following acknowledgement template to provide your name, postnominals, and institutional affiliation as you would like them presented

We thank [NAME], [POSTNOMINALS (MLS, AHIP, etc.)] (Affiliated institution) for peer review of the submitted search strategy.

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please use the following citation for the PRESS checklist when citing the use of PRESS in a journal publication

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment. *PRESS – Peer Review of Electronic Search Strategies: 2015 Guideline Explanation and Elaboration (PRESS E&E)*. Ottawa: CADTH; 2016 Jan. <https://www.cadth.ca/press-peer-review-electronic-search-strategies-0>

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: Yuichiro Nakazawa

Email: Yuichiro_Nakazawa@kagome.co.jp

Date submitted: November 11, 2025

Date requested by: Click or tap to enter a date.

Search Topic or Title:

Effect of lycopene intake on protection against UV-induced skin damage

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

- This is my first submission This is submitted after feedback
 This is an update (the search has been previously used in an evidence syntheses)

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

- This is my first submission This is submitted after feedback
 This is an update (the search has been previously used in an evidence syntheses)

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (ICTRP)

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (ICTRP)

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

In healthy adult subjects, does oral intake of lycopene improve vascular endothelial function compared to oral intake of a test product that does not contain lycopene or has extremely low lycopene concentration compared to the intervention, or no intervention?

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICO, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., **P**atient, **I**ntervention, **C**omparison, **O**utcome, and **S**tudy Design — as applicable)

P Healthy adult subjects (excluding minors, pregnant women, women planning pregnancy, and lactating women).

I Oral intake of lycopene

C Oral intake of a test product that does not contain lycopene or has extremely low lycopene concentration compared to the intervention, or no intervention

O Skin photoprotection assessed by erythema (a^* value), minimal erythema dose (MED), skin lightness (L^* value), erythema index, or D30

S Randomized controlled trials, quasi-randomized controlled trials, non-randomized controlled trials

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

Yes No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Click or tap here to enter text.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

Click or tap here to enter text.

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

#1 (lycopene* OR "Lycopene, (13-cis)-isomer" OR "Lycopene, (7-cis,7'-cis,9-cis,9'-cis)-isomer -" OR "Prolycopene" OR "Pro-Lycopene" OR "Pro Lycopene" OR "Lycopene, (cis)-isomer" OR "LYC-O-MATO" OR "LYCOMATO" OR "LYC O MATO" OR "All-trans-Lycopene" OR "All trans Lycopene") in the Title :Recruitment status is ALL 119 records for 117 trials

#2 (lycopene* OR "Lycopene, (13-cis)-isomer" OR "Lycopene, (7-cis,7'-cis,9-cis,9'-cis)-isomer -" OR "Prolycopene" OR "Pro-Lycopene" OR "Pro Lycopene" OR "Lycopene, (cis)-isomer" OR "LYC-O-MATO" OR "LYCOMATO" OR "LYC O MATO" OR "All-trans-Lycopene" OR "All trans Lycopene") in the Intervention :Recruitment status is ALL 145 records for 143 trials

#3 #1 OR #2 145 records for 143 trials

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: Non-Disclosure

Email: Non-Disclosure

Date completed: November 27, 2025

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were “revision required,” this response must be “revisions required.”).

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

※検索語は問題ありません。

検索日とのタイムラグで、検証時点では合計は“148 records for 146 trials”に増えているようです。

Acknowledgement

Do you wish to be acknowledged?

(If yes, the review team will be advised to add an acknowledgement to any publications related to this work).

Yes No

Please use the following acknowledgement template to provide your name, postnominals, and institutional affiliation as you would like them presented

We thank [NAME], [POSTNOMINALS (MLS, AHIP, etc.)] (Affiliated institution) for peer review of the submitted search strategy.

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please use the following citation for the PRESS checklist when citing the use of PRESS in a journal publication

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment. *PRESS – Peer Review of Electronic Search Strategies: 2015 Guideline Explanation and Elaboration (PRESS E&E)*. Ottawa: CADTH; 2016 Jan. <https://www.cadth.ca/press-peer-review-electronic-search-strategies-0>

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: Yuichiro Nakazawa

Email: Yuichiro_Nakazawa@kagome.co.jp

Date submitted: November 11, 2025

Date requested by: Click or tap to enter a date.

Search Topic or Title:

Effect of lycopene intake on protection against UV-induced skin damage

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

- This is my first submission
- This is submitted after feedback
- This is an update (the search has been previously used in an evidence syntheses)

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

- This is my first submission
- This is submitted after feedback
- This is an update (the search has been previously used in an evidence syntheses)

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

MEDLINE

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

PubMed

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

In healthy adult subjects, does oral intake of lycopene improve vascular endothelial function compared to oral intake of a test product that does not contain lycopene or has extremely low lycopene concentration compared to the intervention, or no intervention?

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICOs, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., **P**atient, **I**ntervention, **C**omparison, **O**utcome, and **S**tudy Design — as applicable)

P Healthy adult subjects (excluding minors, pregnant women, women planning pregnancy, and lactating women).

I Oral intake of lycopene

C Oral intake of a test product that does not contain lycopene or has extremely low lycopene concentration compared to the intervention, or no intervention

O Skin photoprotection assessed by erythema (a* value), minimal erythema dose (MED), skin lightness (L* value), erythema index, or D30

S Randomized controlled trials, quasi-randomized controlled trials, non-randomized controlled trials

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

Yes No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Click or tap here to enter text.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

Click or tap here to enter text.

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

- #1 "lycopene"[Supplementary Concept] OR "lycopene"[MeSH Terms] OR "lycopene**"[All Fields] 7,341
- #2 "plants"[MeSH Terms] OR "vegetables"[MeSH Terms] OR "vegetable**"[All Fields] OR "fruit"[MeSH Terms] OR "fruit**"[All Fields] OR "solanum lycopersicum"[MeSH Terms] OR "lycopersicon esculentum"[All Fields] OR "tomato**"[All Fields] OR "citrullus"[MeSH Terms] OR "watermelon**"[All Fields] OR "water melon**"[All Fields] 622,728
- #3 "dietary supplements"[MeSH Terms] OR "supplement**"[Title/Abstract] 539,154
- #4 #1 AND (#2 OR #3) 3,866
- #5 "randomized controlled trial"[Publication Type] OR "controlled clinical trial"[Publication Type] OR "randomized"[Title/Abstract] OR "placebo"[Title/Abstract] OR "clinical trials as topic"[MeSH Terms:noexp] OR "randomly"[Title/Abstract] OR "trial"[Title] 1,744,582
- #6 "control groups"[MeSH Terms] OR "control group**"[Title/Abstract] OR "control**"[Title/Abstract] 5,268,892
- #7 #5 OR #6 6,169,948
- #8 #7 NOT ("animals"[MeSH Terms] NOT "humans"[MeSH Terms]) 5,113,506
- #9 #4 AND #8 1,153
- #10 "ultraviolet rays"[MeSH Terms] OR "ultraviolet" [All Fields] OR "UV" [All Fields] OR "photodamage" [All Fields] OR "photoaging" [All Fields] OR "photoexposure" [All Fields] OR "skin"[MeSH Terms] OR "skin"[Title/Abstract] OR "erythema"[MeSH Terms] OR "erythema" [Title/Abstract] OR "redness" [Title/Abstract] OR "sunburn"[MeSH Terms] OR "sunburn" [Title/Abstract] OR "minimal erythema dose"[Title/Abstract] OR "MED" [Title/Abstract] OR "erythema index"[Title/Abstract] OR "skin color"[Title/Abstract] OR "pigmentation"[MeSH Terms] OR "pigmentation"[Title/Abstract] 1,252,665
- #11 #9 AND #10 97

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: Non-Disclosure

Email: Non-Disclosure

Date completed: Click or tap to enter a date.

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

3、4、5まとめて表の下にコメント記載します。

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were "revision required," this response must be "revisions required.").

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

#10 について

- Skin Aging[Mesh] . . . 皮膚老化/TH に対応

キーワードとして Wrinkl*[Title/Abstract] OR “solar aging”[Title/Abstract:~2] もご検討ください。

- Skin Pigmentation[Mesh] . . . 皮膚色素沈着/TH に対応

- Suntan[Mesh] . . . 日焼け/TH に対応

キーワードとして Dermatitis Solaris、Light Eruption、Solar Dermatitis、Suntan もご検討ください。
また、Sunburn は語末を sunburn* としてはいかがでしょうか。

Acknowledgement

Do you wish to be acknowledged?

(If yes, the review team will be advised to add an acknowledgement to any publications related to this work).

Yes No

Please use the following acknowledgement template to provide your name, postnominals, and institutional affiliation as you would like them presented

We thank [NAME], [POSTNOMINALS (MLS, AHIP, etc.)] (Affiliated institution) for peer review of the submitted search strategy.

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please use the following citation for the PRESS checklist when citing the use of PRESS in a journal publication

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment. *PRESS – Peer Review of Electronic Search Strategies: 2015 Guideline Explanation and Elaboration (PRESS E&E)*. Ottawa: CADTH; 2016 Jan. <https://www.cadth.ca/press-peer-review-electronic-search-strategies-0>

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: Yuichiro Nakazawa

Email: Yuichiro_Nakazawa@kagome.co.jp

Date submitted: November 11, 2025

Date requested by: Click or tap to enter a date.

Search Topic or Title:

Effect of lycopene intake on protection against UV-induced skin damage

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

- This is my first submission This is submitted after feedback
 This is an update (the search has been previously used in an evidence syntheses)

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

- This is my first submission This is submitted after feedback
 This is an update (the search has been previously used in an evidence syntheses)

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

University Hospital Medical Information Network-Clinical Trials Registry (UMIN-CTR)

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

University Hospital Medical Information Network-Clinical Trials Registry (UMIN-CTR)

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

In healthy adult subjects, does oral intake of lycopene improve vascular endothelial function compared to oral intake of a test product that does not contain lycopene or has extremely low lycopene concentration compared to the intervention, or no intervention?

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICO, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., **P**atient, **I**ntervention, **C**omparison, **O**utcome, and **S**tudy Design — as applicable)

P Healthy adult subjects (excluding minors, pregnant women, women planning pregnancy, and lactating women).

I Oral intake of lycopene

C Oral intake of a test product that does not contain lycopene or has extremely low lycopene concentration compared to the intervention, or no intervention

O Skin photoprotection assessed by erythema (a^* value), minimal erythema dose (MED), skin lightness (L^* value), erythema index, or D30

S Randomized controlled trials, quasi-randomized controlled trials, non-randomized controlled trials

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

Yes No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Click or tap here to enter text.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

Click or tap here to enter text.

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

#1	リコピン	20	
#2	リコペン	8	
#3	プロリコピン	0	
#4	ライコマート	0	
#5	lycopene	25	
#6	prolycopene	0	
#7	LYC-O-MATO	0	
#8	All-trans-lycopene	0	
#9	#1 OR #2 OR #3 OR #4 OR #5 OR #6 OR #7 OR #8		29

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: Non-Disclosure

Email: Non-Disclosure

Date completed: November 27, 2025

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If “B” or “C,” please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were “revision required,” this response must be “revisions required.”).

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

※検索式は問題ございません。

新たに 2025 年 11 月に 1 件登録され、以下の検索語では件数が現時点で変更となり、合計も 1 件増えています。

#1 リコピン 21

#5 lycopene 25

#9 合計 30

Acknowledgement

Do you wish to be acknowledged?

(If yes, the review team will be advised to add an acknowledgement to any publications related to this work).

Yes No

Please use the following acknowledgement template to provide your name, postnominals, and institutional affiliation as you would like them presented

We thank [NAME], [POSTNOMINALS (MLS, AHIP, etc.)] (Affiliated institution) for peer review of the submitted search strategy.

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please use the following citation for the PRESS checklist when citing the use of PRESS in a journal publication

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment. *PRESS – Peer Review of Electronic Search Strategies: 2015 Guideline Explanation and Elaboration (PRESS E&E)*. Ottawa: CADTH; 2016 Jan. <https://www.cadth.ca/press-peer-review-electronic-search-strategies-0>

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: Yuichiro Nakazawa

Email: Yuichiro_Nakazawa@kagome.co.jp

Date submitted: November 11, 2025

Date requested by: Click or tap to enter a date.

Search Topic or Title:

Effect of lycopene intake on protection against UV-induced skin damage

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

- This is my first submission This is submitted after feedback
 This is an update (the search has been previously used in an evidence syntheses)

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

- This is my first submission This is submitted after feedback
 This is an update (the search has been previously used in an evidence syntheses)

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

医中誌 Web

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

医中誌 Web

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

In healthy adult subjects, does oral intake of lycopene improve vascular endothelial function compared to oral intake of a test product that does not contain lycopene or has extremely low lycopene concentration compared to the intervention, or no intervention?

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICOs, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., **P**atient, **I**ntervention, **C**omparison, **O**utcome, and **S**tudy Design — as applicable)

P Healthy adult subjects (excluding minors, pregnant women, women planning pregnancy, and lactating women).

I Oral intake of lycopene

C Oral intake of a test product that does not contain lycopene or has extremely low lycopene concentration compared to the intervention, or no intervention

O Skin photoprotection assessed by erythema (a* value), minimal erythema dose (MED), skin lightness (L* value), erythema index, or D30

S Randomized controlled trials, quasi-randomized controlled trials, non-randomized controlled trials

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

Yes No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Click or tap here to enter text.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

Click or tap here to enter text.

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

#1 Lycopene/TH or リコピン/AL or Lycopene/AL or リコペン/AL or ψ - カロテン/AL or プサイカロテン/AL or psi
カロテン/AL or ψ -Carotene/AL or psi-Carotene/AL or LYC-O-MATO/AL or LYCOMATO/AL or "LYCO MATO"/AL or
ATERONON/AL or "BLAKESLEA TRISPORA"/AL or "CI 75125"/AL or CI-75125/AL or CI75125/AL or "E 160D"/AL or E-
160D/AL or E160D/AL or LYCORED/AL or "MEXORYL SAQ"/AL or MEXORYL-SAQ/AL or "NSC 407322"/AL or NSC-
407322/AL or NSC407322/AL or REDIVIVO/AL or SOLANORUBIN/AL or "TOMAT O RED"/AL or TOMAT-O-RED/AL or
502-65-8/AL or 13018-46-7/AL or トマト/TH or トマト/TA or "Lycopersicon esculentum"/AL or "Solanum
lycopersicum"/AL or Tomato/TA or 赤茄子/AL or アカナス/AL or あかなす/AL or 蕃茄/AL or 唐柿/AL or 小金瓜/AL or コ
ガネウリ/AL or 珊瑚樹茄子/AL or さんごじゅなす/AL or サンゴジュナス/AL or スイカ属/TH or スイカ/TA or Citrullus/AL
or "Water Melon"/TA or Watermelon/TA or 西瓜/AL 2,390

#2 紫外線/TH or 紫外線/AL or "ultraviolet rays"/AL or ultraviolet/AL or rays/AL or ultraviolet/AL or UV/AL or
photodamage/AL or 皮膚老化/TH 皮膚老化/AL or photoaging/AL or photoexposure/AL or 皮膚/TH or 皮膚/AL or skin/AL
or 紅斑/TH or 紅斑/AL or erythema/AL or redness/AL or 日焼け/TH or 日焼け/AL or 日光皮膚炎/TH or 日光皮膚炎 or
sunburn/AL or 最小紅斑量/TH or 最小紅斑量/AL or "minimal erythema dose"/AL or MED/AL or "erythema index"/AL or
"skin color"/AL or 皮膚色素沈着/TH or pigmentation/AL 672,312

#3 #1 and #2 and PT=原著論文,総説 165

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: Non-Disclosure

Email: Non-Disclosure

Date completed: November 26, 2025

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

表の下にコメント記載します。

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were "revision required," this response must be "revisions required.").

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

↓黄色箇所=キーワード重複しており、また rays では広すぎるため削除してはいかがでしょうか。

#2 紫外線/TH or 紫外線/AL or "ultraviolet rays"/AL or ultraviolet/AL or rays/AL or ultraviolet/AL or UV/AL or photodamage/AL or 皮膚老化/TH 皮膚老化/AL or photoaging/AL or photoexposure/AL or 皮膚/TH or 皮膚/AL or skin/AL or 紅斑/TH or 紅斑/AL or erythema/AL or redness/AL or 日焼け/TH or 日焼け/AL or 日光皮膚炎/TH or 日光皮膚炎 or sunburn/AL or 最小紅斑量/TH or 最小紅斑量/AL or "minimal erythema dose"/AL or MED/AL or "erythema index"/AL or "skin color"AL or 皮膚色素沈着/TH or pigmentation/AL 672,312

↓

(修正案) 紫外線/TH or 紫外線/AL or "ultraviolet rays"/AL or ultraviolet/AL or UV/AL or photodamage/AL or 皮膚老化/TH 皮膚老化/AL or photoaging/AL or photoexposure/AL or 皮膚/TH or 皮膚/AL or skin/AL or 紅斑/TH or 紅斑/AL or erythema/AL or redness/AL or 日焼け/TH or 日焼け/AL or 日光皮膚炎/TH or 日光皮膚炎 or sunburn/AL or 最小紅斑量/TH or 最小紅斑量/AL or "minimal erythema dose"/AL or MED/AL or "erythema index"/AL or "skin color"AL or 皮膚色素沈着/TH or pigmentation/AL

Acknowledgement

Do you wish to be acknowledged?

(If yes, the review team will be advised to add an acknowledgement to any publications related to this work).

Yes No

Please use the following acknowledgement template to provide your name, postnominals, and institutional affiliation as you would like them presented

We thank [NAME], [POSTNOMINALS (MLS, AHIP, etc.)] (Affiliated institution) for peer review of the submitted search strategy.

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please use the following citation for the PRESS checklist when citing the use of PRESS in a journal publication

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment. *PRESS – Peer Review of Electronic Search Strategies: 2015 Guideline Explanation and Elaboration (PRESS E&E)*. Ottawa: CADTH; 2016 Jan. <https://www.cadth.ca/press-peer-review-electronic-search-strategies-0>